

A STUDY ON INNOVATIVE PRACTICES OF LEARNING AND HIGHER EDUCATION OF INDIA

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ABSTRACT

There are several developments happened in the field of education sector. Change in technology has a greater impact on the teaching and learning. Higher education is very important in this developing economy because the countries entire development depends on the people with the innovative mind. Higher education is the process of learning, where the utility of skill cannot be achieved without the acquisition of previous skills or previous knowledge. Innovative practices in the education and providing training for staff who are directly involved in the teaching and learning functions will contribute to develop the higher education. There are many online platforms which helps in providing best teaching learning experience. At present competitive world always focus on results rather than efforts. Swayam, MOOC, NPTEL courses are made compulsory in higher education and also experimental learning enhance students to focus on the industrial requirement. These online platforms gives the students best experience of learning. Digital library, e-books and many others innovations are helping students to improve knowledge in many ways. This paper focus on the contribution of innovative practices in higher education for the developments of teaching and learning methods.

Keywords: Higher education, Innovative practices, teaching and learning, online platform.

1. Introduction:

Higher education in India has rapidly changed over years. Many changes and up-gradation have done in the modes of teaching. Innovation in teaching practices are become necessity in present. In the ancient time of our country “Gurukul System” used to revolve around teaching and learning, where the students were educated under the guidance of Guru. In Gurukul System the students used to leave in the same house along with the Guru and all the students were considered equally irrespective of their social standing/ social status. At present, technologies have helped the learners to carry the sources of information’s in tip of their finger. Technology is such a power weapon that can transform learning into much effective way. The best method to improve teaching and learning performance is through innovative practises. Different innovative teaching methods are now in used across the globe. Hybrid teaching is the mixture of campus and digital [1]. Use of technology and electronic gadgets for like teaching and learning assessment is discussed. The reason of using innovative techniques in teaching is to meet the standards of students as expected.

2. Scope of Technology on Higher Education in India:

The quality of programmes, public evaluations, and global rankings of higher education institutions are the key areas of focus for society as higher education systems expand and diversify. [2]. The pandemic situation made the world to realize on the changes and quick adoption of technology in the education field. It will customize the education to every student with expertise teaching across the world. [3] The technology made the way simple to handle and mould the student to progress in a convenient way has teacher can grab the attention of the students much more effectively using the features of technology [4] Online Education system is accessed by the learner very easily because its having the simplest feature which is overtaken the text books or offline materials. One who knows to handle smart gadgets can easily take the benefit and also support the concept online/open education government has taken many initiative programmes [5] Scientific, technological and economical evolution of a country are as dependant on the higher education system as they are on the working class and are on the prior list of the advancement. Online education is essentially the gateway to multifaceted development and prosperity in the country. [6].

3. Objectives of the study:

The core objective of this study is to identify the different innovative techniques of higher education, secondly to know the benefits of innovative techniques in higher education and to determine the impact of innovative techniques in higher education

4. Research methodology:

This paper is developed on the basis of secondary data. The examination of the data includes assessment of published sources. Information regarding innovative educational technologies in India's higher education is gathered from a variety of published sources.

5. Attritions in New learning technology on higher education:

Every changes takes time to have a positive impact. Using innovative practices also seems to be difficult in the initial stage but once after continuous practice one can really take advantage of it. The online platforms may mislead the students to other gaming websites and students easily connect to other networking sources such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter etc. is considered as main drawback of using technology in higher education. It is also observed that when all the students are put together and are asked to use the networking site for the learning session the sites gets either corrupted or jammed. The advertising marketing has boomed in such a way that it is interrupting the learner and driving their attention from the learning to the gaming.

6. Innovative practices for learning in higher education:

Technology has made it very sure to touch all the sectors of higher education from 1980s. the advancement of technology minimised the academic administration process to the instructional process.. Most of the educational institutions consider implementing technology is the special expenditure but it should not be done. It has to be considered as the routine expenditure [7] Present developments made students to learn concepts using smart gadgets such as mobile phone and computer and also made institutions to compulsorily use projectors, videos, subject

materials to teach the concepts. As the study observed, the government presently made compulsion on using ICT in education sector, inculcation of technologies in the classrooms are turning into the favour of the developer/designer rather to the students i.e. the learning apps that are provided for students is user friendly where the students can alter the modules. [8]Technology helps entire higher education system which is untold such as usage of technology in the areas admission, record keeping, generating reports and many other administrative departments of higher education will not only reduce the cost but also significantly improve the efficiency and serves the students effectively.[9]The use of innovative practices made advance technology in higher education helps to improve the quality and accessibility at lower cost in the all the time.[10]Presently the research is growing in the fields of introducing new learning technologies to assists dumb and deaf learners in higher education these technologies translate the study materials into sign languages and helps them to enhance knowledge [11] Every student has access to a top-notch education; therefore, using the outdated methods of chalk and speak to explain topics is inappropriate.12] India is regarded as the second-largest market behind the United States for MOOCs, an online course that allows for open access and limitless enrollment. The platforms for online courses NPTEL and Swayam make studying more engaging and fun. [13].

7. Innovative methods of Higher education:

The combination of various digital media kinds like text, images, audio and videos are used by the teachers to make powerful communication with students to effectively transfer the knowledge.[14] Power point presentation, educational videos on you-tube, Gyan Darshan broadcast, NPTEL video lectures, SWAYAM courses, MOOC are the multimedia tools used in higher education[15]

The power tool which helps students to make decision with reference to framing policy and allocation of resources is Role playing. This technique help the students to engage and interact with their peer group while completing the given task. The students are able to develop inter personal relationship and social behaviour [16].

Flipped Class is a student centred teaching method where students enhance the problem solving skill in the classroom.[17]

Big data is extended its capacity in terms of volume, velocity, and variety will helps higher education offering each student individualised and tailored services as a result of its ability to explore data, comprehend students' behaviour, and understand their needs. [18]

8. Findings of the study:

The innovative techniques in higher education which helps in improving the skills and knowledge of both learner and teacher and contribute to economic development. The students will understand the concept and content as expected than the traditional approach. Innovative methods have a positive impact on teaching learning and students can enhance the knowledge and skills which will result in their performance.

9. Suggestions for improving new learning technologies in Higher Education

in India:

Technology has boomed in such a way that the institutions are not able to ignore the uses of it and are forced to adapt it. In this situation, most of the educational institutions use technology-based education in their classrooms. But as far as study is concerned, innovative practices can be improved in a more efficient way as follows:

- Innovative practices can be used only when the curriculum is supporting to adopt the innovative methods. The universities as to change the curriculum accordingly.
- Providing training to the teachers to use the innovative practices more effectively as the knowledge provider needs to have more knowledge on technical aspects to soothe the problems of learners.
- Vocal feedback and adapting technology-based evaluation techniques of tracing the faults or copied assignments, students can be kept under control and also the innovative skills of the students can be put out. [19]
- To prevent the issues of connecting to outside subject matter through different social media, we have to fix a strong firewall that can protect the applications and also filter the useless apps.

10. Conclusion:

In this current generation, the technology is considered as a flexible and useful teaching and learning tool. For the benefit of the students, teachers, and community, the teachers need to be trained by making effective utilization of technology. [20] This paper discloses the new learning technology on higher education and also provides input on the improvement of technology. When the technological upgradation takes place, the higher education system always gets affected either in a positive way or negative way. Here we made a small study on the technological impact on higher study which helps to overcome the drawbacks of technology on higher education and puts light on the benefits of new learning technology on higher education.

11. References

1. Reinhardt, F., Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, O., Deribo, T., Happ, R. And Nellmuller, S. (2018) 'Integrating Refugees into Higher Education—The Impact of a New Online Education Program for Policies and Practices'. *Policy Reviews in Higher Education* 2(2): 198–226.
2. Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). How innovations and best practices can transform higher education institutions: A case study of SIMS. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 6(2), 83-98.
3. Khairnar. C. M. (2015) Advance Pedagogy: *Innovative Methods of Teaching and Learning*. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, Vol. 5, No. 11, pp 869-872.
4. Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2019). Management of ICCT underlying technologies used for digital service innovation. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 4(2), 110-136.

5. Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2015). An innovative education model to realize ideal education system. *International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM)*, 3(3), 2464-2469.
6. Bonk.C.J. (1998) Cummings, "Recommendations for placing the student at the center of web-based learning," *Educational Media International*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 82- 89.
7. Younis Ahmad Sheikh (2017)" *Higher Education in India: Challenges and Opportunities*", Vol.8, No.1
8. Gunn. E. (2014) "Using clickers to collect formative feedback on teaching: a tool for faculty development," *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, vol. 8, no. 1, article 11.
9. Joyce Waddell (2015)" *The Role of Technology in the Educational Process* "Michigan state university.
10. ALLY, M. and TSINAKOS, A. (2014) *Increasing Access through Mobile Learning*. Vancouver: Commonwealth of Learning and Athabasca University.
11. Dr. Sintu Ganai (2019)"*A multidisciplinary Online Journal of Netaji Subhas Open University, INDIA*", Vol.2 No.2 (July 2019), ISSN: 2581-5415
12. Hans N. Weiler, Stanford University (2005), "*Higher Education in India: Reflections on some Critical Issues*", First Edition.
13. Jai Mohan Pandit,(2019) "*What India needs at higher education institutions*", Financial Express Journals.
14. Roger G. Baldwin –"*Technology in Education*"School,higher education-current trends.
15. Mohammed F. Fahmy –"*Thinking About Technology Effects on Higher Education*"-The journal of technology studies.
16. Reed Sheard (2018) -"*The role of Technology in the Great Higher Education Transformation*"Forbes Technology Council.
17. King S. B. (2014) "Graduate student perceptions of the use of online course tools to support engagement," *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 130-132
18. Susan Grajek (2018) - "*Technology and the remarking of Higher Education: A Longer View* "Communities and research, for EDUCAUSE
19. N.Vinoth and K.Nirmala (2017)" *Deaf students Higher Education System Using E-learning* "Journal of Education and learning.Vol.11 (1) pp.41-46,DOI:10.11591/edulearn.v11i15131
20. Jamshed N.Lam –"*Technology in the Classroom*"- technology tutorials.